

The Integration of Agile Principles in Traditional Project Management Frameworks: A Comparative Study

Paper Id : 18089 Submission Date : 15/07/2022 Acceptance Date : 19/07/2022 Publication Date : 25/07/2022

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.8351966

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Ahmad Ali

Research Scholar
Management
Lords University
,Alwar, Rajasthan, India

Mayank Agrawal

Associate Professor
Management
Lords University
Alwar, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

This comparative analysis dives into the incorporation of Agile principles within conventional project management frameworks. Its aim is to investigate the alignment, advantages, and hurdles associated with this evolving project management landscape. In the face of growing demands for adaptability and responsiveness, businesses must fuse the iterative, customer-centric techniques of Agile with the structured, step-by-step approaches of traditional project management. The analysis provides an all-encompassing framework for contrasting Agile and traditional project management methods across critical aspects, such as project lifecycle, flexibility, documentation, stakeholder engagement, risk management, team structure, and change management. It highlights the potential benefits of this integration, including heightened agility, enhanced stakeholder engagement, improved product quality, and decreased project risks. Simultaneously, it tackles the challenges, encompassing cultural mismatches, complex resource allocation, documentation issues, and skill set prerequisites. In summary, this analysis offers valuable insights to organizations striving to navigate the intricate realm of project management by amalgamating Agile principles with traditional methodologies. It underscores the significance of aligning project management practices with organizational requisites and culture, enabling businesses to harness the strengths of both paradigms to achieve project success in a continually changing environment.

Keywords Agile Principles, Traditional Project Management, etc.

Introduction

In today's swiftly changing business environment, organizations confront a dual challenge: the necessity for structured project management to ensure predictability and control, coupled with the demand for agility to respond effectively to rapidly shifting market dynamics and customer preferences. Traditional project management frameworks like Waterfall or PRINCE2 have long served as the foundation of project execution, offering a systematic approach to planning and managing projects with clearly defined scopes. In contrast, Agile methodologies, including Scrum, Kanban, and Lean, have gained popularity due to their iterative, customer-centric, and adaptable nature. These divergent approaches have proven effective in their respective contexts, generating growing interest in exploring their fusion [1].

Aim of study

The objectives are as follows:

1. To investigate the incorporation of Agile principles into conventional project management frameworks, with a specific emphasis on aligning and exploring the advantages of this evolving project management landscape.
2. To establish a comprehensive framework for evaluating and contrasting Agile and traditional project management approaches across various key aspects.
3. To underscore the potential advantages of merging Agile principles with traditional methodologies, encompassing heightened agility, improved stakeholder involvement, elevated product quality, and decreased project risks.
4. To aid businesses in harnessing the strengths of both Agile and traditional project management paradigms to attain project success in an ever-changing environment where adaptability and responsiveness hold paramount importance.

Review of Literature

In recent years, the field of project management has undergone significant transformations, spurred by the ever-shifting landscape of industries and technologies. As organizations actively seek more flexible and responsive project management approaches, the concept of agility has come to the forefront. This compilation of research papers thoroughly examines various aspects of agile project management, including its fusion with traditional methodologies and its application across a wide range of domains. From the transition from Traditional Project Management (TPM) to Agile Project Management (APM), to the evolution of hybrid methodologies and the complexities encountered when implementing agile practices in large-scale projects, these studies illuminate the dynamic nature of project management in today's modern context. Ley explore these papers to gain valuable insights into the ongoing revolution in agile project management.

Ciric, D., et al. (2019) discuss the prominence of agility in today's context, primarily in software development literature. They highlight the agile software development methodology's gradual and iterative nature, focusing on flexibility, adaptability to change, continuous progress, and strong interaction. They note the growing recognition of agile's relevance beyond software development and aim to provide a comprehensive overview of strategies for introducing agile into traditional project management. Their study also investigates reasons for adopting agile and the challenges involved, employing a distributed questionnaire through the Project Management Institute network [24].

Sanchez, F., et al. (2019) introduces Agile Project Management (APM) as a replacement for Traditional Project Management (TPM), both in software and non-IT sectors. The paper presents the concept of "agilification" as a smooth transition from TPM to APM, emphasizing the need for APM maturity models and scenarios. It proposes adapting the Project Management Maturity Model (P3M) to APM and offers a conceptual framework with behaviour ontologies and tools for agilification. A case study on schedule management audit illustrates these concepts [24].

Papadakis et al. (2020) explore the practice of combining various project management approaches into hybrid and adaptive methods tailored to specific project and team needs. They conduct a systematic literature review from 2000 to 2020, analysing 1,121 articles and selecting 98 for further investigation. Their results provide insights into agile project management frameworks, challenges, and best practices for implementing hybrid approaches, contributing to project management knowledge and organization of agile and hybrid methods [25].

Bushuyev et al. (2020) delve into organizational development in project, program, and project portfolio management systems, focusing on agile transformation drivers. They examine changes in the decision-making paradigm within agile project and program management and explore leadership formation and development in the context of Agile transformation. Their study includes competency-based models for agile leadership, identifying behavioural competencies like self-reflection, communication, teamwork, and negotiation for project managers as agile leaders [26].

Diem G. (2021) investigates the practical use of hybrid project management, comparing it to traditional and agile models using 15 established Critical Success Factors (CSF). The study employs a quantitative approach with an online survey of project management professionals in Germany. Findings reveal that hybrid project management differs from both traditional and agile approaches depending on the CSF. Guiding principles for choosing project management paradigms are formulated, benefiting practitioners by aiding decision-making regarding project management approaches [27].

Santos, P. D. O., & de Carvalho, M. M. (2022) address the challenges organizations face when scaling agile methods to large projects. They conduct a literature review and identify 53 barriers categorized into six main areas and 32 benefits grouped into three categories. Requirement management emerges as a critical factor impacting both barriers and benefits. Their findings can serve as a basis for questionnaires to explore these aspects further in practice [28].

Main Text**Rationale for the Study**

The integration of Agile principles into conventional project management frameworks represents a critical juncture in the field of project management. Agile methodologies excel in fostering responsiveness, embracing change, and engaging stakeholders

continuously, while traditional approaches excel in providing structure, governance, and comprehensive documentation. Recognizing this, organizations are increasingly seeking to strike a harmonious balance between these two paradigms. This study is driven by the urgent need to comprehend how this integration can be effectively achieved, with its rationale grounded in several key pillars [1]:

1. **Project Success in a Dynamic World:** In today's business landscape, marked by constant change, project success is no longer solely determined by adhering to initial plans but by an organization's capacity to swiftly adapt to market shifts and evolving customer expectations. The study aims to explore how integrating Agile principles can enhance project outcomes in this context [2].

2. **Maximizing Resources:** Effective resource allocation is a pivotal challenge for organizations managing multiple projects. The study seeks to examine how integrating Agile can optimize resource allocation and utilization within traditional project management frameworks, ultimately enhancing efficiency [2].

3. **Enhancing Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving stakeholders and gathering feedback are pivotal to project success. The study delves into how the integration of Agile principles can facilitate continuous stakeholder collaboration and communication, ensuring that projects remain aligned with business objectives.

4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

5. This study holds substantial significance in the domains of project management and organizational strategy for various reasons:

6. **Bridge the Gap:** It aims to bridge the gap between the adaptability of Agile methodologies and the structure of traditional project management, providing valuable insights into how organizations can leverage the strengths of both paradigms [3].

7. **Practical Guidance:** Through the examination of real-world case studies and examples, this study intends to offer practical guidance to organizations contemplating Agile integration, assisting them in navigating the complexities of this process.

8. **Strategic Decision-Making:** As organizations contemplate their project management approaches in a continually evolving world, the findings of this study can inform strategic decision-making, enabling them to select the most suitable approach for their specific projects and objectives [3].

9. **Academic Contribution:** This research contributes to the academic discourse surrounding project management methodologies by offering a comprehensive analysis of the integration of Agile principles into traditional frameworks.

In summary, this study embarks on an exploration of the integration of Agile principles into traditional project management frameworks, recognizing its profound implications for project success, resource optimization, and stakeholder engagement. By investigating the synergy, benefits, and challenges of this integration, it aims to provide valuable insights for organizations striving to thrive in today's dynamic business landscape [3].

TRADITIONAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT APPROACHES

Traditional project management frameworks encompass well-established and structured methodologies that have been utilized for many decades to strategize, execute, and oversee projects. These frameworks are distinguished by their sequential and linear project management approach, comprising clearly delineated phases and processes. Key traditional project management frameworks encompass Waterfall, PRINCE2 (Projects IN Controlled Environments), and the Critical Path Method (CPM). Below are the defining characteristics of traditional project management frameworks [4]:

1. **Sequential Phases:** Traditional project management frameworks generally entail a sequence of precisely defined phases that must be completed in a specific order. These phases commonly include initiation, planning, execution, monitoring, and closure, each having its own set of tasks and deliverables [4].

2. **Thorough Planning:** Traditional methodologies prioritize comprehensive planning before project execution commences. This planning phase encompasses the definition of

project scope, objectives, timelines, resource requirements, and a detailed project plan, with the goal of minimizing uncertainties and risks before the project starts.

3. **Limited Changes:** Once a project is underway in a traditional framework, modifications to project scope or requirements are typically discouraged or tightly controlled. The emphasis is on adhering to the original plan to maintain predictability.

4. **Documentation-Centric:** Traditional project management relies extensively on documentation. Every project phase typically necessitates the creation of comprehensive documents, including project charters, project plans, requirements documents, design specifications, and progress reports [4].

5. **Well-Defined Roles:** Traditional project management often features distinct and clearly outlined roles and responsibilities for team members. These roles often follow a hierarchical structure, with a project manager at the apex, responsible for overall project direction.

6. **Early-Stage Risk Management:** Risk management is predominantly addressed during the project planning phase in traditional frameworks. Risks are identified, analyzed, and mitigated before execution commences.

7. **Focus on Deliverables:** Traditional project management places a strong emphasis on delivering the project's final product or outcome. Project success is frequently measured by the timely and on-budget completion of these deliverables.

8. **Client Involvement at the Beginning and End:** Stakeholder or client involvement is generally more limited in traditional frameworks, with clients playing a substantial role during project initiation (setting requirements) and project closure (acceptance).

9. **Change Control Procedures:** Traditional methodologies incorporate formal change control procedures to be followed if project changes are deemed necessary. These processes are often designed to minimize scope changes and uphold project predictability [4].

10. **End-Stage Quality Control:** Quality assurance and control activities are typically concentrated toward the conclusion of the project when final deliverables are being produced and tested.

11. While traditional project management frameworks possess strengths in providing structure, predictability, and a well-defined path to project completion, they are frequently critiqued for their limited adaptability to change and responsiveness to evolving customer needs. Agile methodologies, with their focus on adaptability and customer collaboration, have thus gained prominence as an alternative or complementary approach to project management in today's rapidly evolving business landscape [4].

Details of Waterfall, PRINCE2 and CPM: [5]

Waterfall: Waterfall is a conventional project management methodology that follows a sequential and linear approach to project execution. It divides the project into distinct phases, with each phase building upon the previous one [5]. There are various types of key feature and components like phases, through planning, minimal changes, documentation, well-defined roles, risk management and quality control.

PRINCE2 (Projects IN Controlled Environments): PRINCE2 is a process-driven project management methodology that emphasizes controlled project environments. It provides a structured framework for managing projects, known for its adaptability and governance. There are various types of key feature and components like Process-Oriented, Emphasis on control, flexibility, stakeholder involvement and focus on deliverables. [6]

Critical Path Method (CPM): The Critical Path Method (CPM) is a network-based project management technique used for scheduling and planning projects with well-defined tasks and dependencies. There are various types of key feature and components like network-based , deterministic, identifying critical path, resource agnostic, used for planning and control and application in construction and engineering [7].

In summary, Waterfall follows a sequential, phased approach; PRINCE2 provides a structured, adaptable framework with a strong focus on governance, and CPM is a

network-based scheduling technique used for projects with clear task dependencies. Each methodology suits different project management needs and is chosen based on project requirements and characteristics.

Key Principles and Features of Agile Approach

Agile methodologies are a group of project management approaches that prioritize flexibility, collaboration, and customer-centricity. There are various types of key feature and components like customer-centricity, iterative and incremental development, embracing change, collaboration and communication, self-organizing teams, working software as the primary measure of progress, sustainable pace and continuous improvement [14].

Project Management Methodologies: Agile vs. Traditional:

1. **Approach to Change:** Agile methodologies embrace change and allow for flexible adaptation to evolving project requirements. Traditional methodologies, such as Waterfall, resist changes to project scope once execution begins, often requiring formal change control processes.

2. **Project Planning:** Agile planning is adaptive and incremental, with a focus on short-term planning for the next iteration. Traditional planning is comprehensive and detailed, with extensive upfront planning before execution begins [15].

3. **Documentation:** Agile emphasizes lightweight documentation and values working software over comprehensive documentation. Traditional methodologies require extensive documentation at each project phase [15].

4. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Agile methodologies encourage ongoing stakeholder engagement and collaboration throughout the project. Traditional approaches may limit stakeholder involvement to project initiation and closure phases.

5. **Testing and Quality Assurance:** Agile promotes continuous testing and quality assurance throughout the development process. Traditional methodologies often conduct testing primarily at the end of the project [16].

6. **Project Control:** Agile provides control through frequent inspections, transparency, and regular adaptation to changes. Traditional methodologies control projects through predefined processes and documentation [16].

7. **Project Delivery:** Agile delivers increments of working software iteratively throughout the project. Traditional methodologies aim to deliver the entire project scope at the project's end.

8. **Risk Management:** Agile identifies and mitigates risks continuously throughout the project. Traditional methodologies focus on risk management primarily during the project planning phase [17].

9. In summary, Agile methodologies prioritize customer collaboration, flexibility, and incremental development, whereas traditional project management approaches emphasize comprehensive planning, documentation, and control. The choice between Agile and traditional methodologies depends on the project's nature, complexity, and the organization's goals and culture. Some organizations may even adopt hybrid approaches to combine the strengths of both methodologies.

Integrated / Hybrid Approach

Hybrid project management models offer a strategic approach that combines elements from both Agile and traditional project management methodologies. This fusion capitalizes on their respective strengths while effectively addressing specific project requirements and organizational constraints. Here, we present an overview of three prevalent hybrid models [17]:

Hybrid Model: Blending Agile and Traditional Approaches- The hybrid model seamlessly integrates Agile and traditional project management methodologies to strike a harmonious balance between adaptability and structure. It excels in scenarios where certain project aspects benefit from Agile practices, while others necessitate the

predictability inherent in traditional methods [17]. There are various types of key feature and components like selective adoption, flexibility and control and customization.

Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) Implementations- SAFe stands as a structured framework designed to extend Agile practices across large-scale enterprises. It provides a methodical approach for assimilating Agile principles throughout various tiers of an organization, ranging from individual teams to portfolio management [17]. There are various types of key feature and components like hierarchical structure, agile principles, program increments (PIs), release planning and continuous improvement [18].

Kanban Integration into Traditional Project Management- Kanban, a Lean and Agile methodology, places emphasis on visualizing work, managing workflow, and optimizing processes. It can be seamlessly incorporated into traditional project management approaches to enhance visibility and efficiency. There are various types of key feature and components like visual workflow, limiting work in progress (WIP), pull system, continuous improvement and adaptability [19].

Key Characteristics:

In conclusion, hybrid project management models, SAFe implementations, and the integration of Kanban into traditional project management methodologies offer strategies that harmonize the structured nature of traditional project management with the agility and adaptability inherent in Agile principles. Organizations have the flexibility to choose the model that best aligns with their specific project requisites, organizational culture, and the imperative to optimize project management practices across different facets of their operations [20].

5. Benefits of Integration

Benefits of Incorporating Agile Principles into Conventional Project Management Approaches:

1. **Enhanced Responsiveness to Change and Market Shifts:** Integrating Agile principles empowers project teams to swiftly adapt and respond to alterations in project requirements, market conditions, or customer preferences. Agile's iterative development cycles, such as Scrum sprints, enable teams to promptly integrate fresh insights and modify project direction as necessary [20]. By aligning with market dynamics, organizations can swiftly capitalize on emerging opportunities and promptly address evolving challenges [20]. **Continuous Feedback:** Agile methodologies emphasize regular interactions with stakeholders, including customers and end-users, ensuring that the project consistently meets their needs and expectations [21]. Agile promotes close collaboration among team members, stakeholders, and customers, fostering better communication and understanding of project objectives [21]. Agile's transparency in progress and decision-making builds trust and cultivates a sense of ownership among all stakeholders.

2. **Higher-Quality Deliverables and Increased Customer Satisfaction:** Agile methodologies prioritize delivering high-quality, tested, and functional increments of the product in each iteration, reducing the risk of defects and ensuring customers receive a valuable and reliable product. Agile places the customer at the core of the development process, resulting in products that better align with their expectations and needs. Frequent releases of working software or products enable customers to witness progress and provide feedback, ultimately boosting their satisfaction.

3. **Risk Mitigation and Early Issue Detection:** Agile projects consistently identify, assess, and mitigate risks, with teams actively monitoring project progress and making adjustments to minimize potential issues [22]. Agile's short iterations and regular feedback loops facilitate early identification of issues and obstacles, enabling timely resolution and preventing issues from escalating [22]. Agile's adaptability enables teams to promptly respond to emerging risks or issues, adjusting project plans as needed to minimize adverse impacts.

4. **Efficiency and Productivity Improvements:** Agile methodologies assist organizations in efficiently allocating resources based on immediate project needs and priorities. Agile practices, such as limiting work in progress and prioritizing value delivery, minimize wasted effort and resources on low-priority tasks. Agile encourages teams to reflect on their processes and seek ways to enhance efficiency and productivity through regular retrospectives [23].

Conclusion In summary, merging Agile principles with traditional project management methodologies represents a strategic approach that offers numerous advantages for organizations aiming to excel in today's dynamic and competitive business landscape. By blending the structured, sequential nature of traditional project management with the flexibility, adaptability, and customer-centric focus of Agile methodologies, organizations can enhance project success and overall operational excellence. This integration yields a plethora of benefits, including heightened responsiveness to shifting market dynamics, improved engagement and collaboration with stakeholders, the delivery of superior products and services leading to increased customer satisfaction, proactive identification and mitigation of project risks, and the realization of efficiency and productivity improvements. These advantages collectively empower organizations to remain agile, innovative, and competitive in an ever-changing environment.

As organizations embark on the Agile integration journey, it is crucial to acknowledge that the choice between Agile and traditional project management approaches should be guided by the specific needs, complexity, and objectives of each project. Some projects may thrive with full-scale Agile implementation, while others may find success by embracing hybrid models or selectively integrating Agile practices. The key lies in aligning project management practices with the organization's culture, goals, and the ever-evolving market demands. To conclude, the integration of Agile principles with traditional project management frameworks equips organizations with the tools and strategies necessary to navigate the intricacies of modern business and harness the strengths of both paradigms, ultimately achieving sustained project success and fostering business growth.

Integrating Agile principles into conventional project management frameworks offers a multitude of significant advantages. This integration enables organizations to swiftly respond to change and market dynamics, enhances stakeholder engagement and collaboration, results in higher-quality deliverables and greater customer satisfaction, mitigates project risks through continuous monitoring and adaptation, and drives efficiency and productivity gains by optimizing resource allocation and reducing waste. These benefits collectively contribute to the success of projects and bolster an organization's ability to thrive in a dynamic and competitive business environment.

Limitation of the Study Traditional project management models, such as Waterfall and PRINCE2, have been widely used for decades but come with several limitations and drawbacks [8]. Traditional project management models, exemplified by methodologies like Waterfall and PRINCE2, have enjoyed widespread use over the decades; however, they do come with various constraints and disadvantages:

1. **Limited Adaptability to Change:** Traditional models exhibit a distinctive trait of being inflexible and sequential. Once the project plan is set in motion, they tend to resist alterations to project scope or requirements, which may render them less suitable for projects within dynamic or swiftly evolving environments [8].
2. **Handling Uncertainty:** Traditional models heavily rely on comprehensive initial planning to mitigate uncertainties. Nevertheless, in intricate projects or those marked by evolving requirements, accurately predicting and planning for every possible scenario can prove challenging. Consequently, unexpected challenges may arise during project execution [8].
3. **Involvement of Customers:** Traditional models often engage customers or stakeholders primarily at the project's outset and conclusion. This limited interaction throughout the project's duration can result in misunderstandings or misalignment between project outcomes and actual requirements.
4. **Extended Time to Deliver Value:** Traditional models tend to provide value at the project's conclusion, following a protracted planning and execution process. This can present a drawback, particularly in industries where delivering incremental value rapidly is imperative [9].
5. **Risk Management:** While traditional models do address risk management, their focus is often concentrated during the early planning stages. This can lead to inadequate risk assessment and management as the project progresses, especially when unforeseen risks emerge.
6. **Resource Allocation:** Traditional models may not adeptly handle resource allocation and utilization. Addressing resource constraints and optimization may be lacking, potentially resulting in delays and inefficiencies [9].
7. **Overwhelming Documentation:** Traditional models frequently necessitate extensive documentation at each project phase. While documentation is crucial for maintaining records and accountability, an excess of paperwork can become time-consuming and may not always contribute substantial value.
8. **Limited Collaboration:** Traditional models may not foster collaborative teamwork to the same extent as Agile methodologies. This constraint can impede creativity and innovation and curtail opportunities for continuous improvement.
9. **Absence of Real-Time Monitoring:** Traditional models may lack real-time monitoring and

reporting mechanisms. Consequently, project managers may have limited visibility into project progress until later stages, which can pose challenges in addressing issues promptly.

10. Client Satisfaction: Owing to the limited engagement of customers and the potential inflexibility of traditional models, clients may not be entirely content with the final deliverables if their needs have evolved during the project [10].

11. Managing Scope Creep: Traditional models may encounter challenges in effectively managing scope creep (unplanned changes or additions to the project scope). Since they discourage changes once the project is underway, scope adjustments can lead to project delays or budget overruns [10].

12. Complex Project Management: For highly intricate projects with numerous interdependencies, traditional models may struggle to provide the necessary flexibility and responsiveness, which are vital for navigating complexity effectively.

13. In summary, while traditional project management models offer structure and predictability, they may not be the optimal choice for projects in swiftly evolving environments or those necessitating frequent customer collaboration and adaptability. Recognizing these limitations, organizations often turn to Agile and hybrid approaches to address these challenges and enhance overall project management effectiveness.

References

1. Zasa, F. P., Patrucco, A., & Pellizzoni, E. (2020). Managing the hybrid organization: How can agile and traditional project management coexist?. *Research-Technology Management*, 64(1), 54-63.
2. Bogdanova, M., Parashkevova, E., & Stoyanova, M. (2020). Agile project management in governmental organizations—methodological issues. *IJASOS-International E-Journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, 6(16), 262-275.
3. Layton, M. C., Ostermiller, S. J., & Kynaston, D. J. (2020). *Agile project management for dummies*. John Wiley & Sons.
4. Ploder, C., Dilger, T., & Bernsteiner, R. (2020). A Framework to Combine Corporate Budgeting with Agile Project Management. In *Software Engineering (Workshops)*.
5. Papadakis, E., & Tsironis, L. (2020). Towards a hybrid project management framework: A systematic literature review on traditional, agile and hybrid techniques. *The Journal of Modern Project Management*, 8(2).
6. Rush, D. E., & Connolly, A. J. (2020). An agile framework for teaching with scrum in the IT project management classroom. *Journal of Information Systems Education*.
7. Jiménez, V., Afonso, P., & Fernandes, G. (2020). Using agile project management in the design and implementation of activity-based costing systems. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10352.
8. Zavyalova, E., Sokolov, D., & Lisovskaya, A. (2020). Agile vs traditional project management approaches: Comparing human resource management architectures. *International journal of organizational analysis*, 28(5), 1095-1112.
9. Marović, I., & Bulatović, G. (2020). Development of a hybrid agile management model in local self-government units. *Tehnički vjesnik*, 27(5), 1418-1426.
10. Tolbert, M., & Parente, S. (2020). *Hybrid project management: Using agile with traditional PM methodologies to succeed on modern projects*. Business Expert Press.
11. Raharjo, T., & Purwandari, B. (2020, January). Agile project management challenges and mapping solutions: A systematic literature review. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Software Engineering and Information Management* (pp. 123-129).
12. de Oliveira Santos, P., & de Carvalho, M. M. (2020). Lean and agile project management: An overview of the literature exploring complementarities. *The Journal of Modern Project Management*, 8(2).
13. Žužek, T., Kušar, J., Rihar, L., & Berlec, T. (2020). Agile-Concurrent hybrid: A framework for concurrent product development using Scrum. *Concurrent Engineering*, 28(4), 255-264.
14. Bakhit, H., & Villmer, F. J. (2020). Agile methodology for physical product development: limitations and solutions. *O-VILLMER*, 131.
15. Getyengana, N. (2020). *Effective implementation of a Hybrid project management methodology combining agile and traditional methods for IT-based projects in South African organisations* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Pretoria).
16. Esteki, M., Gandomani, T. J., & Farsani, H. K. (2020). A risk management framework for distributed scrum using PRINCE2 methodology. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, 9(3), 1299-1310.
17. Fateev, N., & Zaporozhets, I. (2020). AGILE-METHODOLOGY IN SHIPBUILDING PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN CONDITIONS OF CLUSTER INTEGRATION. *Scientific Journal of Polonia University*, 43(6), 307-311.
18. Vieira, M., CR Hauck, J., & Matalonga, S. (2020, December). How explicit risk management is being integrated into agile methods: results from a systematic

literature mapping. In Proceedings of the XIX Brazilian Symposium on Software Quality (pp. 1-10).

19. Anjum, S. K., & Wolff, C. (2020, November). Integration of agile methods in automotive software development processes. In 2020 IEEE 3rd international conference and workshop in Óbuda on electrical and power engineering (CANDO-EPE) (pp. 000151-000154). IEEE.

20. de Souza, M. L. P., de Souza, W. C., Freitas, J. S., de Melo Filho, L. D. R., & Bagno, R. B. (2020). Agile roadmapping: a management tool for digital entrepreneurship. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 69(1), 94-108.

21. Khoza, L. T., & Marnewick, C. (2020). Waterfall and agile information system project success rates-a South African perspective. *South African Computer Journal*, 32(1), 43-73.

22. Dumrak, J., Mostafa, S., & Hadjinicolaou, N. (2020). Using analytic hierarchy process to evaluate implementation barriers of agile project management in australian project environments. In *The 10th International Conference on Engineering, Project, and Production Management* (pp. 277-286). Springer Singapore.

23. Vejseli, S., Rossmann, A., & Connolly, T. (2020). Agility matters! Agile mechanisms in IT governance and their impact on firm performance.

24. Ciric, D., Lalic, B., Gracanin, D., Tasic, N., Delic, M., & Medic, N. (2019). Agile vs. Traditional approach in project management: Strategies, challenges and reasons to introduce agile. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 39, 1407-1414.

25. Sanchez, F., Micaelli, J. P., & Bonjour, E. (2019). A Step for Improving the Transition Between Traditional Project Management to Agile Project Management Using a Project Management Maturity Model. *The Journal of Modern Project Management*, 7(1).

26. Dilger, T., Ploder, C., Haas, W., Schöttle, P., & Bernsteiner, R. (2020, October). Continuous Planning and Forecasting Framework (CPFF) for Agile Project Management: Overcoming the. In *Proceedings of the 21st Annual Conference on Information Technology Education* (pp. 371-377).

27. Papadakis, E., & Tsironis, L. (2020). Towards a hybrid project management framework: A systematic literature review on traditional, agile and hybrid techniques. *The Journal of Modern Project Management*, 8(2).

28. Bushuyev, S. D., Bushuiev, D. A., Bushuieva, V. B., & Bojko, O. O. (2020). Agile transformation by organisational development projects. *Bulletin of the National Technical University "KhPI". Series: Strategic management, portfolio, program and project management*, (1), 3-10.

29. Diem, G. (2021). Agile and traditional project management: comparing agile, traditional and hybrid project management practices (Doctoral dissertation, Heriot-Watt University).

30. Santos, P. D. O., & de Carvalho, M. M. (2022). Exploring the challenges and benefits for scaling agile project management to large projects: a review. *Requirements engineering*, 1-18.